

Project: AEGEUS, Grant Agreement Number: 101099210

Deliverable

D4.6 | Data Management Plan 2

Work package 4

Project Information

Grant Agreement Number	101099210
Project Full Title	A Novel EEG Ultrasound Device for Functional Brain Imaging and Neurostimulation
Project Acronym	AEGEUS
Funding scheme	EIC Pathfinder Open
Start date of the project	2023-03-01
Duration	4 years
Project Coordinator	Fraunhofer MEVIS
Project Website	eic-aegeus.eu

Author(s): Julia Müller, Sven Rothlübbers

Status: Published

Date: 2025-08-04

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Table of Contents

Overview and scope of this document.....	3
Version history.....	3
Definitions	3
Data Summary.....	4
FAIR data.....	6
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	6
Making data accessible.....	6
Making data interoperable.....	10
Increase data re-use.....	11
OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS	11
ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	12
DATA SECURITY.....	12
OTHER ISSUES.....	12

Overview and scope of this document

Data generation and its analysis aim at developing a radically new diagnostic and therapeutic device for neurological applications which combines a highly innovative ultrasound component for brain imaging and focused stimulation of brain regions with advanced electrophysiological measurements of neural activity. This document presents the **second version** of the Data Management Plan (DMP) in the AEGEUS project and provides an overview of the data management policy applied to datasets generated within the Project. This DMP identifies the main datasets and describes research data management during the project, as well as how and what parts of the datasets will be openly shared, will be made accessible for verification and re-use, will be curated, and preserved. The goal of this DMP is to facilitate effective internal data management and make data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). The DMP is, in fact, a living document and it will be updated and further refined with the project's progress. It is also important to remark that this DMP reflects the provisions established by the project contracts and complements the planned project exploitation, dissemination and IPR procedures.

Version history

2025-06-25 V1-1 Initial Version, Julia Müller

2025-08-04 V1-2 Updated by Sven Rothlübbers and curated by Julia Müller

Definitions

CT – Computed Tomography

DICOM – Digital Imaging and Communication in Medicine

EDF – European Data Format

EEG - Electroencephalography

MR(I) – Magnetic Resonance (Imaging)

NIfTI – Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative

ORB – “Open Research Binary” format by Fraunhofer IBMT

US - Ultrasound

Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

In order to conserve resources and progress faster in the project, existing data should be used as far as possible. The project will utilise both open and internal data sources, i.e. the data for this project will be sourced from multiple origins, including open data repositories such as Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>).

Important data are e.g. publicly available Brain Atlas Data. Also publicly available data, as tissue parameters, which are necessary for simulations will be used from public data bases or publications. Data already available from the project partners should also be used. In particular, morphological MRI data of the brain and EEG data. (see table 1).

AEGEUS will use the already available public and internal data as a starting point to develop and optimise the devices that are specifically needed for the project.

State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

Especially in the case of medical data collected from patients, there is a possibility that these data cannot be passed on by the clinical project partners for data protection reasons. So far, however, no such data that may be relevant to the project has been found. At the current stage of the project, it is also not possible to foresee whether such data will exist.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

List of public and private data that may be publicly available, generated as part of the project or already existing at one site. These data may be shared within or outside the consortium. Data protection regulations are observed and the transfer of personal data is avoided.

Table 1: List of data

Data	Type	Format	Origin/Provenance
Brain atlas data	brain parcellation data	DICOM	Publicly available https://www.leaddbs.org/helpsupport/knowledge-base/atlasresources/cortical-atlas-parcellations-mni-space/ Hammersmith Atlas: http://brain-development.org/brain-atlases/adult-brain-atlases/adult-brain-maximum-probability-map-hammersmith-atlas-n30r83-in-mni-space/
EEG data	Recorded electrode signal data	edf, hdf5, mat	Mostly generated in the project, maybe some already existing data from the clinical project partners (SALK)
Surface Data	Surfaces of structures, e.g. skull bone	mesh, stl, wem	Project generated
Segmentation Data	Segmentation of Structures in the head (Skull,	NIfTI	Project generated

	White Matter, Gray Matter...)		
US data	RAW Data, Images, derived data	ORB, DICOM, jpg, png	generated in the project
MR data	Images, functional or structural data	DICOM, NIfTI	Mostly generated in the project, maybe some already existing data from the clinical project partners (SALK, FhG)
CT data	Images	DICOM	Only from project partners or public sources
Evaluation	Text, tables, photos, images	pdf, docx, pptx, txt	Project generated
Reports			
Deliverables			
Publications			

To be updated during the course of the project.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The purpose for accurate collection of data being generated within the AEGEUS project is to give researchers the ability to answer relevant research questions and facilitate the repetition and validation of the study to other researchers. Data collection is essential for the achievement of the objectives of the project, it helps with maintaining the integrity of research, making informed decisions and ensuring quality assurance. Further, the objectives of disseminating and communicating the outcomes will benefit by the correct and systematic acquisition of data.

The size of the data that will be generated within the AEGEUS project varies from a few KB for documents, over MB for simple EEG recordings up to GB for multimodal EEG-US recordings. The data collection is based on repeated experiments, i.e. data is acquired from participants and patients, partly twice for reliability testing. Therefore, the sum of data to be generated is in the range of several TB. The exact size that will be generated until the end of the project is not yet clearly defined as it depends on the sampling rate, and number of channels of the EEG part of the final system and the resolution of the to-be generated images, as well as on the number of subjects and the duration of the recordings. See also table 1.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Throughout the project experimental data will be recorded of artificial phantoms, volunteers, and patients. This includes EEG and ultrasound data as well as derived data. Such data can have high temporal resolution and therefore have large file sizes.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Some of the acquired data is necessary to solve current project issues. These remain internal to the project, dissemination outside of the project does not make sense.

Other data could be mainly useful to academia and research institutes for reproduction and verification. This includes in particular the scientific publications.

As part of the project, we will collect data from stakeholders, i.e., patient organisations, neurologists, and public health-care providers, through surveys to collect end-user opinions about the new system.

FAIR data

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery?

Yes

What metadata will be created?

Author, Year, Dataset standard, Persistent Identifier, Date, File Size, File Type, data related descriptions (e.g. for EEG /US data)

What disciplinary or general standards will be followed?

The EngMETA standard will be followed.

In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

The DataCite (<https://datacite.org/>) Metadata Schema will be implemented throughout the project. Metadata for each dataset will contain specific information according to the nature of the dataset, like creator, time reference, experimented conditions, parameters of technical equipment, processing software information, variable names, etc.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Associated keywords will be optimized to allow data exchange and enhance re-use possibilities, unless temporary intellectual property restrictions or safety issues apply.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes

Making data accessible

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

AEGEUS will adapt and implement the following five open science practices:

- i) Open access:
Our deliverables that are marked as public (PU) in the participant portal will be

published on Zenodo with a link on our website, while any open research output (e.g., datasets, publications, practices, abstracts) will be deposited in online repositories (e.g., Zenodo, Open Research Europe), providing open access (green and/or gold). Our list of open research outputs along with the repository and provisional date of upload, in line with FAIR principles and the rule “as open as possible, and as closed as necessary” is provided in table 2.

- ii) Open and early sharing of research:
Open and early sharing of data will be achieved as follows:
 - a. preregistration at an appropriate platform (e.g., the Centre of Open Science or aspredicted.org), sharing time stamped, read-only versions of publications
 - b. uploading of open datasets on Zenodo.
- iii) Measures to ensure reproducibility:
All consortium members will take the necessary steps to make the results transparent by providing access to data and other results needed for the validation of our future findings. Adequate protocols and methodologies will be applied in all project phases, ensuring precision of research outputs, while the implementation of our Management and Progress monitoring tasks (WP4) will ensure the validity and quality of the project’s processes and results. This will include internal peer review processes for all deliverables.
- iv) Open peer review:
Our publications will be offered with green and/or gold open access, e.g., to Open Research Europe, an open peer review venue, enabling us not only to share our results rapidly but also to facilitate open, constructive research discussions to enhance their quality and relevance.
- v) Involvement of all knowledge actors:
During the entire project duration, we will involve key knowledge actors via target group and stakeholder engagement at the cross-regional and European levels, such as mutual learning workshops, synergies with projects, policy roundtable, and much more.

Table 2: List of open research outputs

Name	Type	Format	Upload date	Repository
AEGEUS - Exploitation and Dissemination Plan 1. Zenodo	D	Pdf	2023	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10955974
AEGEUS - Data Management Plan 1	D	Pdf	2023	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10953674
AEGEUS - A Novel EEG Ultrasound Device for Functional Brain	Poster	Pdf	2023	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10962869

Imaging and Neurostimulation				
AEGEUS - A Novel EEG Ultrasound Device for Functional Brain Imaging and Neurostimulation	Presentation	Pdf	2023	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10962888
AEGEUS - Clinical Specification	D	Pdf	2023-05-31	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10955621
Gambosi, B., et al. (2025). Towards Brain State Classification with Functional Ultrasound Imaging. IX Congress of the National Group of Bioengineering (GNB).	Abstract	Pdf	2025-06-30	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774004
Buda, C., et al. (2025). A Deep Learning Approach to EEG Subcortical Source Localization. IX Congress of the National Group of Bioengineering (GNB).	Abstract	Pdf	2025-06-30	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775285

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Yes.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier?

Yes.

Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes, for publications. No, for other data.

Will all data be made openly available?

Yes, except during IP applications.

If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement. If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

The data produced will be stored locally in designated, regularly updated project folders to make data easily accessible on demand. The data generated under the project will be discoverable, identifiable and locatable. The PI is responsible for the data produced, processed and published by the institution.

Embargo period, when required, is respected.

Not all data will be made openly available due to privacy concerns, legal restrictions, or contractual obligations, for example, personal information of human participants in experiments will be strictly confidential. If necessary, an embargo may be applied to allow time for publication or to seek protection of intellectual property. The duration of the embargo will be determined based on the specific needs of the project, with the understanding that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Data access will be provided through a free and standardized protocol, ensuring that authorized users can efficiently access the data. Access restrictions may be applied during and after the project, and the identity of individuals accessing the data will be verified through secure authentication methods.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?

Yes. The data will be made accessible on request. Sharing of human-derived data requires approval from local authorities (ethical committee, data protection authority) and a non-disclosure agreement.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project? How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

No restrictions, unless patents are involved or data is kept confidential because it is related to human participants in experiments. In the case of patents, the data will be made available after the patent has been filed. In the case of patents, shareability of the data depends on local regulations and whether the data to be shared includes sensitive information.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)? Metadata: Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement?

No need for a committee. Yes, it follows CC0.

If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

It will follow CC0.

How long will the data remain available and findable?

For at least 10 years after the end of the project.

Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Yes

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data?

Yes, the collected ultrasound data will be in proprietary Fraunhofer IBMT file format.

Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Most data will be stored using standard non-proprietary file formats e.g. JPG, CSV, TXT, EDF, DICOM. The proprietary file format of collected ultrasound data can be converted into a python / numpy based format.

Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?

The descriptions of procedures and protocols and explanation accompanying and documenting the data will be written in English, using a formal, accessible, and broadly applicable style for knowledge representation. In case special vocabulary or acronyms are used, these will be defined in the associated metadata. For certain terms we may refer to open, external vocabularies (e.g. the open definition of a given use license, the reference to the funders and grants, through OpenAIRE). When included, each referenced external piece of metadata will be qualified by a resolvable URL address. Finally, standard text files will be used for most numerical simulations and data analysis scripts, which will also consist of Jupyter notebooks, combining textual explanations, code, and figures generated by the code. The JSON scheme of Zenodo will be adopted as internal representation of metadata, enabling the ease of exporting them to other popular formats (e.g. Dublin Core, MARCXML, etc.).

Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices?

Yes.

Which ones?

EngMeta.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Yes.

Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them? Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Yes.

Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Readme files in .txt format with clear instructions.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?

Yes.

Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Yes. Data will be licensed in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Information about cleaning, data quality assurance procedures, methodology, as well as variables' definitions, units of measurements, software dependencies, and in general data structure will be included in "readme.txt" or "readme.md" files deposited together with data.

OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.). Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Research outputs of physical nature (samples, materials etc.) will be stored in the respective laboratories under appropriate conditions for preservation of all material properties. This will be indicated in the respective metadata files, archived in the Zenodo repository. Access to these materials will be granted upon request and materials can be re-used as long as prevailing quality and quantities allow for it. Methods, including software, workflows, protocols and models will be published alongside the resulting data in open access journals and can be accessed as part of the metadata in Zenodo repository.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

How will these be covered?

Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

How will long term preservation be ensured?

Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Cost related management (i.e. collection and short-term storage) will be covered by the individual beneficiary's institutional unit costs. For long-term data preservation no costs are expected, as the Zenodo data repository is free of charge. Data management activities will be overlooked by the coordinating institution, and guidance (with respect to correct data management) will be provided as needed. Duration of data preservation will be linked to Zenodo and therefore be in accordance with the EU OpenAire recommendations.

DATA SECURITY

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Data and metadata uploaded in Zenodo will be stored online and offline, as independent replicas, for the lifetime of the repository. This is associated with an experimental program, currently defined for a very long-time horizon during the next 20 years.

OTHER ISSUES

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Yes.

- a) For **internal sharing of experimental data** (EEG, US, evaluations), an S3 storage with personalised user access was created. Access is granted to the project participants actively involved in data generation and analysis.

- b) For **internal sharing of pseudonymized study data** (EEG, US, questionnaires) between the study sites (SALK, UNAK) and the evaluating partners (UROME, UNITOV), a project specific instance of mediri's study data management platform mTRIAL will be provided. mTRIAL is a validated web-based software supporting pseudonymized upload of medical image data as well as data collection via electronic forms.

Solutions a and b are hosted in German data centres complying to highest data security standards.

